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Scrutinizing Re-Syllabification in English Consonant Clusters through Interlanguage Theory

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this qualitative study is to study ineptness of Urdu speakers in pronunciation of English consonant clusters, applying the postulates of the theory of Interlanguage, presented by Larry Selinker in 1972. A list of different consonant clusters was prepared. Fifty participants were selected with Urdu background from different walks of life. Their articulations were recorded and then phonetically transcribed. The findings reflect that the Urdu speakers, under the influence of their L1, cannot pronounce English consonant clusters in an accurate manner. They insert a vowel/ə/ at different levels in English consonant clusters, and this insertion results into re-syllabification of English consonant clusters. The study is significant, since it supports academics who are ambitious in raising Pakistani English to an International standard.

Keywords: English consonant clusters, re-syllabification, stress-pattern of Urdu, stress-pattern of English, Interlanguage theory

Introduction

This qualitative study aims to justify the ineptness of Pakistani Urdu speakers in English consonant clusters pronunciation through the lens of Interlanguage developmental phonology presented in 1972. It explores the phenomenon of re-syllabification due to differences in stress patterns of English and Urdu. It also attempts to analyze the difference between the template structures of both the languages and highlight the differences between nonnative production and native production of English consonant clusters. The study looks into the speaker's mindset as they pronounce words with syllabic consonants. It focuses on how native language (Urdu) influences the second language and how words with syllabic consonants are spoken. This study is significant for multidisciplinary fields like morphology, sociolinguistics, world languages, ELT and ESL, etc. After determining the impact of L1, this study is based on a phonetic examination of English vocabulary words which are commonly used in daily life. Phonological norms tell speakers of a language about potential phonemic combinations and multiple/alternative pronunciations (Farran,2022). In other words, the term "morphology" may be replaced by the phonological rules. The explanation is because the phoneme, which is the fundamental building block of language, also affects the morphology of words. As a result, the potential morphological combinations for creating a meaningful word form with different pronunciations are significant (Mousikou et al., 2015). International Phonetic Association. In a connected speech, phonological differences are also unavoidable and unintentional (Port et al., 2005).

Speech sounds or segments are important components of human languages. Every language has a unique sound system, and each language chooses sounds differently in terms of quantity and kind. When a learner deliberately starts the process of learning a second language or a foreign language, he or she may quickly observe that the sounds of the second language are more or less unique from his or her own mother tongue and aren't even generated in the same way. Due to some differences between the phonemic features of two languages; L1 and L2, the second-language learners often try to adjust the target language's sound system to more closely resemble their native tongue. In this situation, creating a first language sound system for second language learners will provide important insight into the challenges and barriers to learning a second language.

A learner's mistakes in the target language's rules are often in fact "correct" by the

rules of an "inter- language" invented by the learner as a temporary and sufficiently workable substitute, according to the "Interlanguage theory". This theory assumes that a learner's mind is active and independent enough to draw its own generalizations when confronted with a new language. Insisting on punishing any and all such "errors" undermines the student's ability to self-direct their learning

Interlanguage Theory

An American linguist, Larry Selinker for the first time coined the term interlanguage in a Cambridge International forum article on the notion of Second Language Acquisition published in 1972. Interlanguage, according to him, is the linguistic system of learner language that develops when adults attempt meaningful communication in a language they are learning (IL). Selinker's interlanguage notion gave rise to the first research topics in the burgeoning field of second language acquisition (SLA). In updated form, it continues to offer a strong, comprehensive foundation for research in this field (Selinker, 2015).

Selinker further established that interlanguage systems occupy a position basically between L1 and L2. Despite being distinct from L1 and L2, it has parallels with both in that it refers to the shift from beginning understanding to native competence in a language. In phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, and culture, it differs from both the target language and native language of the learner. The most significant component of the interlanguage theory is that the language an adult learner produces while striving to communicate successfully in a foreign language is systematic on all levels. It is possible to study the phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics of language. At its heart, the interlanguage system is self-contained and patterned. It is a separate transitional language system whose evolution may be characterized using cognitive and sociolinguistic processes.

Acquisition and usage of interlanguage are often unconscious processes that the learner cannot analyze introspectively. In fact, the learner is often oblivious of the linguistic characteristics of the language he or she is speaking, erroneously supposing that the linguistic forms used in IL are "the same " as those used in NL and TL. When asked about the interlanguage norms they use in their own spontaneous, meaningful communication, students will be unable to provide a satisfactory response. Individuals may alternatively refer to TL principles they have formally learned in the classroom, but these are not the interlanguage norms they use while focusing on meaning. One of Selinker's most controversial claims is that interlanguage fossilized, or ceased to evolve before becoming identical to the language system of the destination. Adults who are learning a second language seldom attain their desired level of accuracy in the target language (Selinker, 2013).

English Language Teaching in Pakistan

In Pakistan, English is being taught as a second language, since it is both an official language and lingua franca (Seedi et al., 2025). The research's central proposition is that Pakistani Urdu speakers' English pronunciation deviates from the standard British English pronunciation which is due to the influence of Urdu phonological principles and can be justified through the lens of Interlanguage development. The cause is the observation of different English vocabulary pronunciations, which, more intriguingly, are equally comprehensible among L2 English speakers in Pakistan. In this regard, the current study aims to provide additional knowledge about the interlanguage phonology of English linguistic learners from Pakistan (Haidar & Fang, 2019).

Urdu Phonological System

Urdu's phonological system has a significant influence in the formation of second language phonology among Pakistani language learners, especially in terms of language transfer. Ellis (1994, p. 316) hypothesized this phenomenon, stating that "it is well acknowledged that transfer is more prominent at the level of the sound system than at the level of syntax." On the other hand, Nemser (1960) reported in Selinker (1992, p. 177), finds in his research that "in terms of the learning of phonological components, conventional Contrastive Analysis predictions might sometimes lead to accurate and sometimes wrong outcomes." Nonetheless, the current research employs Selinker's IL "interlanguage" theory as a theoretical framework since it "provides a broad description of how L2 learning occurs'."

In Urdu, syllables are pronounced evenly while in English, stress syllables are placed at regular intervals (Khan, 2025). Furthermore, both languages have different phonetic and phonological principles in addition to orthographic differences in their writing and speech. Similar to how consonants and vowels have different shapes, English spellings and sounds can be misleading when it comes to pronunciation because English is a non-phonetic language. In the writing system of Urdu, however, pronunciation is represented by the sounds and spellings of words because Urdu has a phonemic writing system. Researcher has observed that students of English language learners who speak Urdu as their first language make significant phonological variations when pronouncing English speech in particularly consonant clusters and stress patterns because there is a significant discrepancy between the stress patterns and systems of the two languages (Sarwat et al., 203).

In learning English as a second or foreign language, a vital role is played by the correct pronunciation and significance of stress patterns can never be neglected for vocalization of correct pronunciation because influence of L1 pronunciation effects accent patterns of L2 as it is said by Rod Ellis (1985) that many hardships are faced by L2 learners due to the first language influence especially in Pakistan and various languages are spoken in this society as L1 e.g. Urdu, Punjabi, Sindhi, Pashto and Balochi. (Rahman et al., 2019). Nevertheless, there are specific areas where Urdu is spoken as L1 and English is spoken as L2, and these issues are concerned to this study because these are existing there prominently due to the L1(Urdu) and L2(English) difference although in Pakistan the speakers of Punjabi, Urdu, Pashto, Balochi and Sindhi learn English as a second language. Pakistani community learns English as EFL and ESL. It frequently has been observed that there exists a difference between L1 and L2 and learners' L1 knowledge tampers L2 proficiency.

Stress Patterns of English and Urdu

This study further compares the syllable structures and word stress patterns of English and Urdu to identify the types and degrees of differences between the two languages. Due to some similarities and differences between Urdu and English in terms of phonological features, this study aims to fill a gap in the prior literature by focusing on the interlanguage development in epenthesis of English consonant clusters by Urdu speakers learning English as an L2, and by providing solutions for both students and teachers. Since variations in stress patterns may influence both pronunciation and meaning, so this study aims to underline the significance of knowing English stress patterns for speakers of Urdu who also use English as a second language (L2). Tamandani (2017) defines stress as the amount of energy expended during the creation of a syllable. The difference between stressed and unstressed vocalic sound on the word level is a common description of lexical stress. The syllable prominence

is dependent on two factors: the loudness of the syllable and the length of the duration. Overall pitch supports and is related with length and greater intensity of the syllable in this way. In Phonology, the main function of stress is to discern between emphasis and contrastive stress.

The original concept of interlanguage was limited to adults studying second languages. However, another research in Canadian French immersion programmes indicated that children created interlanguages that seemed to be calcified and influenced by NL transfer. This phenomenon seemed to have sociolinguistic causes, since the youngsters only got information from their native-speaking instructor and contributed substantial non-native input to one another. In general, they lacked enough opportunities or incentives to innovate. Swain (1995) characterized attempts to develop interlanguage via meaningful interactions with others as "comprehensible output" (Ortega, 2012).

Adjemian (1976) argued that interlanguages should be considered natural languages. Interlanguages are the result of the same universal grammar that creates national languages, according to this perspective. Interlanguages, like natural languages, must conform to language universals. Unlike other natural languages, ILs get fossilized in cases when the parameters of the NL have already been determined and a target language with different parameter settings must be learnt owing to complicated modifications (Kasper, 2011).

The third component of the interlanguage hypothesis is an increasing concern with the manner in which interlanguage forms alter and evolve in different social circumstances (Tarone, 1979, 1988). Interlanguage is much more fluent, grammatical, and transfer-free in some social circumstances than in others, showing that social context is critical for interlanguage development. Under some settings, social surroundings may alter the developmental sequences of SLA (Lakshmanan, 2009). When discussing their academic competence, international teaching assistants may be more fluent and grammatically perfect than when discussing common topics such as their favorite dish or bicycles (Selinker & Douglas, 1985). According to Bayley and Tarone's (2012) analysis of variationist SLA research, learner language variation is systematic. Hundreds of variationist investigations have shown that variation in interlanguage creation has major consequences for data elicitation and processing in research (Preston, 1989, 2002; Tarone, 2000; Geeslin & Gudmestad, 2010). Because the production of specific interlanguage forms changes systematically according to social environment, task, subject, focus on form, interlocutor, and other factors, variationist academics insist that these variations be recorded.

Various phonological rules, such as assimilation, deletion, voicing, insertion, segment alternation, aspiration, nasalization, etc., have been explored among different languages (Iyiola, 2014). This research investigates the stress pattern and phenomenon of vowel epenthesis in English syllable-initial, medial and final consonant clusters, as indicated previously. It uses Selinker's (1972) "Interlanguage" theory as a framework to explain the pronunciation phonotactics of Pakistani English speakers. This theory serves as the basis for this research.

The IL theory of Selinker (1972) is adopted and adapted as a framework for the present study since it has been decided to be adequate and applicable based on an assessment of the numerous trends and ideas concerning the phonological phonotactics in English and Urdu. Otherwise, it is because it corrects for wrong words and "provides an overview of how L2 acquisition occurs". In addition, instead of contrastive analysis (CA) theory the 'interlanguage hypothesis led to an altogether new era of second language research and teaching and constituted a substantial break

from contrastive analysis hypothesis'. Moreover, According to Selinker's research a 'contrastive perspective of units applying simultaneously to three linguistic systems – NL, TL, and IL' existed, but conventional CA was limited to two linguistic systems - NL and TL (Selinker, 1992, Selinker, 1988).

Research Method

This study investigates the stress patterns and the vowel epenthesis in English consonant clusters of Pakistani Urdu speakers' pronouncing English consonant clusters. The premise of this study is that Pakistani Urdu speakers' pronunciation of English consonant clusters is directly influenced by the phonological rules of Urdu. The objective of this study is to highlight the issue of variation in the pronunciations of English consonant clusters of Pakistani Urdu speakers. The pronunciations are tested against the British accent as a benchmark. Mispronunciation is described as "incorrect or inaccurate pronunciation" by the Oxford English Dictionary. There are some definite discrepancies to this extent, and the mispronunciation is rather a heated issue (Areshka, 2025).

Sample Population

The data were collected from Urdu speakers. Only graduate people in different disciplines were selected for this process. Highly qualified people, especially in the field of English language were strictly avoided with a notion that such people are conscious of these pronunciation errors. They range in age from 18 to 55 and have finished their undergraduate and graduate. They are therefore expected to receive equal exposure to both Urdu and English. The people with educational backgrounds in some good English medium schools were deliberately avoided by the researcher. It was due to the fact that the target of this study was the common Pakistani Urdu speaking people and so that they might be exact representatives of the target population. An English script covering all phonemes in various phonemic combinations has been given to them.

Form of the Test

For data collection in this study, a list of different consonant clusters was prepared. The focus was put on the specific areas where the consonant clusters are two or three at coda position. After selection of words, these were put under different categories of consonant clusters. The subject's pronunciation was captured using a portable mac air computer. The tool used for recording is known as multimedia voice recorder. The microphone was set nearby to ensure recording clarity and avoid background noise. Specifically, the microphone was linked to the speakers as a single unit (headphone). The speech data was subsequently analyzed by Windows Media Player, version 8000 HZ.

The chosen vocabulary contains numerous occurrences with the same spellings but with various phonemic alternation, syllable templates, syllable counts, and stress that result in numerous alterations in their speech and pronunciations. The "standard" pronunciation is used, and it is cross-checked, using the Oxford English Dictionary. In this section the collected recorded data is transcribed according to British Pronunciation and compared to the data which is collected by recordings of Pakistani Urdu speakers.

Phonetic Transcription

The obtained data were phonetically transcribed. It was first transcribed according to the pronunciation of English and then according to the pronunciation of Urdu speakers. The collected data was examined on the basis of the British pronunciation model.

Syllabification and re-syllabified

The words were syllabified and re-syllabified by the researchers.

Data Analysis

The similar pattern has been seen in Pakistani Urdu speakers' English speaking. The overgeneralization and hypercorrection of Urdu phonological norms in speakers' English speech (Hulst, 1979) may be the cause. Therefore, after taking into account the significant impact played by Urdu phonological principles, phonological differences in English pronunciation. It has been acoustically studied. The fundamental explanation for Pakistani Urdu speakers' various pronunciations of the phonetic-scripts of English speech is that Urdu, like other languages, contains sound change rules (Farooq & Mumtaz, 2016).

This study is focused on different syllabification of consonant clusters of English by the Urdu speakers. Consider for example the following table which shows the difference in syllabification between both the languages.

“mb Clusters”

In the analysis of the ‘mb clusters’, it is found that the native speakers drop terminal /b/, because when two bilabial stops are together, one is dropped, but the Urdu speakers consciously pronounce it following the spelling system. They insert a /ə/ at the coda position like bomb, comb e.t.c.

Table: 4.1

English Consonant Clusters	Syllabification of Consonant Clusters in English	Re-syllabification due to the epenthesis of /ə/
Bomb	bɔ:m	bɔ:m.bə
Comb	kɔ:m	kɔ:m.bə
Tomb	tu:m	tɔ:m.bə
womb	'wu:m	'wu:m.bə
lamb	'læm	'læm.bə

“mp Clusters”

In the ‘mp clusters’, the native speakers drop /p/ but Urdu speakers consciously pronounce it following the spelling system. This is mainly due to the fact that the Urdu language allows only zero or one consonant in the onset of syllables. It can allow not more than two consonants in coda position. It is due to this fact that they insert /ə/ at the end. Here another challenge was seen, that is the spellings of final consonant clusters, the people who learn the language by reading and by imitating their own so called English teachers fail in development of their pronunciation skill.

Table: 4.2

English Consonant Clusters	Syllabification of Consonant Clusters in English	Re-syllabification due the epenthesis of /ə /
Camp	kæms	Kæm.pə
Lamp	læms	læm.pə
Mump	məm	məm.pə
Lump	lʌmp	lʌm.pə
Jump	dʒʌmp	dʒʌm.pə
Stump	stʌmp	stʌm.pə
Stamp	stæmp	stʌm.pə

“nk Clusters”

In the ‘nk clusters’, the native speakers stop at /k/, on the other hand the Urdu speakers insert /ə/ after /k/, this problem does not arise in the connected speech, but in case of pronunciation of these clusters as individual words, the Urdu speaker insert /ə/ after /k/.

Table: 4.3

English Consonant Clusters	Syllabification of Consonant Clusters in English	Re-syllabification due the epenthesis of /ə /
Pink	pink	pin.kə
Link	link	lin.kə
Sink	sink	sin.kə
Wink	wink	win.kə
Bank	bænk	bæn.kə
Rank	rænk	ræn.kə
Tank	tænk	tæn.kə
Thank	θænk	θæn.kə

“θs Clusters”

In the ‘θs clusters’, the native speakers drop /θ/ but our people do not and they insert /ə/ between /θ/ and /s/ due to the main reason mentioned above. On the other hand, English spelling does not account for the allophonic variation between aspirated and unaspirated voiceless stops. As a result, English voiceless stops without aspiration are produced in all situations by Pakistani Urdu speakers of English. In addition to this, they discovered that Pakistani English speakers produce English /r/ as a rhotic and /t d/ as retroflex, in contrast to British English speakers.

Table: 4.4

English Consonant Clusters	Syllabification of Consonant Clusters in English	Re-syllabification due the epenthesis of /ə /
Depths	dəps	də.p.θəs
Fifths	fɪfs	fɪf.θəs
Twelfths	t.welfs	t.welf.θəs
Truths	tru: θs	truθəs

“rm Clusters”

In the ‘rm clusters’, the native speakers drop /r/ when it is followed by some consonant but our people pronounce it following the spellings as well as being unaware of this rule and they also insert /ə/ between / r/ and /m/. As a result, adding a phoneme increases the number of syllables in a word and leads to various pronunciations of monosyllabic words.

Table: 4.5

English Clusters	Consonant	Syllabification of Consonant Clusters in English	Re-syllabification due the epenthesis of /ə /
Alarm		əla:.m	ə.la:rə.m
Warm		wɔ:.m	wɔ:r.ə.m
Farm		fa:.m	fa:rə.m
Charm		'tʃɑ:m	'tʃɑ:rə.m

Discussion

The findings indicate that L2 pronunciation is dominated by L1. The results of this study provide crucial information about the variances and types of English pronunciation of native Urdu speakers while speaking English consonant clusters as their L2. It is observed that English pronunciation is crucial for intelligibility, although this difference may be explained by considering interlanguage development. Getting better at this will hide the fact that English is not your first language. Students who do not participate in communicative activities in class do not improve their communication abilities. In the communicative learning programme, the instructor also plays a unique function as a "speech coach" or "pronunciation coach," depending on the situation. Instead of only correcting the learner's errors, the "speech coach" provides knowledge, occasionally provides models, provides constructive criticism, and sets high standards before them while being aware of their major difficulty

areas. First language acquisition is more comprehensive than second language acquisition because learners utilize their native language for everyday communication. Because there is only one linguistic system the learner's mind is attempting to comprehend and the learner is constantly exposed to the language, L1 learners have no difficulty producing the majority of words in their language after puberty; however, L1 features play a role in the learning of L2, causing a clash between the systems of L1 and L2. According to (Kissova, 2020), the phonetics and phonology of the first language have a significant influence on the pronunciation of the second language. Contrastive Analysis is required for analyzing the influence of L1 on L2.

Conclusion

English and Urdu are quite different languages from each other. Without getting proper knowledge and training of pronunciation, it is difficult for Urdu speakers to come up with English consonant clusters. Stress patterns, syllabification rules and templates of both the languages are different. The people who learn English mostly through reading are quite unable to pronounce words well. They handle English consonant clusters according to the stress pattern of Urdu and consciously put effort into pronouncing even those words which are dropped by the native speakers. Moreover, due to differences in template structures of both the languages, the problem of Urdu speakers with English consonant clusters is natural and can be justified on account of Interlanguage development. Furthermore, language learning happens gradually rather than all at once. This "interlanguage", which underpins understanding and production of the target language, is neither similar to L1 or L2. The student alters his or her interlanguage at each step by adding or eliminating rules or by reorganizing the entire system.

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